

Syntheses, spectral characterization and antimicrobial properties of zinc carboxylates containing nitrogen donor as ancillary ligand

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Abstract : Three new dimeric inorganic-organic hybrid compounds $[\text{Zn}_2(\text{mal})_2(\text{aniline})_4]$ (1), $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) and $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3) (mal = malonate, 4-HOBz = 4-hydroxybenzoate, py = pyridine) have been synthesized from aqueous methanol at room temperature and characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance, FT-IR, ¹H NMR, and mass spectral analysis. Results of spectroscopic analysis suggest that the compounds are dinuclear and each zinc ion is tetra coordinated and bridged by carboxylate oxygen atoms. Compounds exhibit moderate to appreciable antimicrobial activity. Compounds $[\text{Zn}_2(\text{mal})_2(\text{aniline})_4]$ (1) and $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3) are moderately active against bacteria *Bacillus pumilus*, however, $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) is found to be significantly active towards *Bacillus pumilus*.

Keywords : Synthesis, characterization, antimicrobial properties, inorganic-organic hybrid.

Introduction

Zinc carboxylates are of great interest owing to their role in biochemical systems, catalysis and material chemistry¹⁻³. Carboxylic acids play key role in metabolic pathways of many fundamental biochemical processes^{4,5}. Mono as well as dinuclear zinc carboxylate complexes are of importance in biochemical processes^{6,7}. Apart from the bio active role of zinc carboxylates, design and synthesis of MOPs (metal-organic polymers) and MOF's (metal-organic frameworks) with carboxylic acids continue to generate interest due to their potential applications in catalysis, adsorption, optical, magnetic, bio-medical materials and also due to their interesting network architectures⁸⁻¹¹. Carboxylic acid exhibit various coordination modes, such as terminal monodentate, chelating and various modes of bridging coordination of two, three or even more metal centers¹² and also function as hydrogen bond acceptors and donors in assembling supramolecular complexes¹³. Although a number of carboxylate based coordination compounds are known, however, the rational design and synthesis of novel metal carboxylates by employing new synthetic tools, varying the nature of reactants, synthetic conditions are still under active investiga-

tion. In addition to carboxylic acids the nitrogen donors, such as pyridine, aniline and related molecules also exhibit good ligating ability. Use of such ligands lead to the formation of compounds with a wide range of physical, chemical and biological properties, spanning a broad spectrum of reactivity and stability¹⁴. As a sequel of our interest in zinc-carboxylate chemistry, we have prepared zinc carboxylates involving carboxylic acids incorporating nitrogen donor as ancillary ligand. The present work deals with synthesis, characterization and studies of antimicrobial properties of dinuclear zinc carboxylates involving pyridine/aniline as ancillary ligand.

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

Chemicals used were all reagent grade products. Solid state infrared spectra (FT-IR) were recorded as KBr disc using Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 100 FT-IR spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with Bruker Avance II 200 MHz spectrometer at ambient temperature using CD₃OD as solvent. C, H, N contents of the compounds were determined by micro analytical methods and mass spectra of the compounds were obtained using Waters

model Q-ToF Premier mass spectrometer. Zinc was estimated volumetrically by complexometric titration with EDTA using Erio-T as indicator¹⁵.

Synthesis :

(i) *Synthesis of $[Zn_2(mal)_2(aniline)_4]$ (1) (mal = malonate)* : To a methanolic solution (20 mL) of malonic acid (0.208 g, 2.0 mmol) an aqueous solution (5 mL) of zinc acetate dihydrate (0.219 g, 1.0 mmol) was added dropwise with stirring. To the resultant homogeneous solution was added 0.5 mL (0.45 g, 5 mmol) of aniline slowly with continuous stirring. The resulting mixture was stirred further for *ca.* 1 h at room temperature. The mixture was filtered to remove any undissolved impurities. The clear solution so obtained was kept undisturbed for two to three days when colorless crystalline product was deposited. Yield ~65%, based on zinc.

(ii) *Synthesis of $[Zn_2(4-HOBz)_4(aniline)_2] \cdot H_2O$ (2) (4-HOBz = 4-hydroxybenzoate)* : To a methanolic solution (20 mL) of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (0.276 g, 2.0 mmol), 5 mL of an aqueous solution of zinc acetate dihydrate (0.219 g, 1.0 mmol) was added dropwise with stirring. To this solution was added 0.5 mL (0.45 g, 5.0 mmol) of aniline slowly with continuous stirring. The resultant clear solution so obtained was further stirred for a period of *ca.* 1 h, filtered and kept undisturbed in open air. Colorless crystalline product was deposited after 2–3 days. Yield ~62%, based on zinc.

(iii) *Synthesis of $[Zn_2(4-HOBz)_4(py)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$ (3) (py = pyridine)* : To a methanolic solution (20 mL) of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (0.276 g, 2.0 mmol) was added 0.5 mL (0.49 g, 6.2 mmol) of pyridine slowly with stirring. To this mixture was added 10 mL of an aqueous solution of zinc acetate dihydrate (0.219 g, 1.0 mmol) slowly with continuous stirring. The resultant homogeneous mixture

so obtained was further stirred for a period of *ca.* 1 h. The solution was filtered to remove any undissolved impurities and left undisturbed in a freezer for 4–5 days when colorless crystalline product was deposited. Yield ~68%, based on zinc.

Determination of antimicrobial activity :

Complexes have been tested *in vitro* to assess their growth inhibitory activity against four bacterial species viz. *Bacillus pumilus* (Gram-positive), *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive), *Vivrio cholerae* (Gram-negative) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative). Tetracycline was used as standard. Antibacterial activity of the complexes were evaluated by means of ‘cup-plate’ method¹⁶. Stock solutions (10^{-3} mol L⁻¹) of the complexes were prepared in ethanol. Each plate was inoculated with 100 μ L of bacterial suspension and 25 μ L of stock solution was added to each cup. The plates containing bacteria were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The positive antibacterial activity was ascertained based on the growth of inhibition zone. The results of the antimicrobial studies are summarized in Table 3.

Results and discussion

A solution phase reaction of zinc acetate dihydrate, respective carboxylic acid and aniline or pyridine in methanol at room temperature afforded new dinuclear zinc carboxylates containing aniline/pyridine, $[Zn_2(mal)_2(aniline)_4]$ (1), $[Zn_2(4-HOBz)_4(aniline)_2] \cdot H_2O$ (2) and $[Zn_2(4-HOBz)_4(py)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$ (3) in reasonably good yield. Synthesized dinuclear complexes are air stable, non-hygroscopic and soluble in organic solvents. Complexes were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance measurement, FT-IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectrometry. Molar conductance measurements of 1, 2 and 3 in methanol solution exhibit values of 15–20 Ω^{-1}

Scheme 1. General reaction scheme for synthesis of complexes.

Table 1. Analytical data of the compounds

Compound	Found (Calcd.) (%)				Color	Yield (%)	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)
	C	H	N	Zn			
$[\text{Zn}_2(\text{mal})_2(\text{aniline})_4]$	51.36 (51.23)	4.03 (4.01)	7.84 (7.97)	18.34 (18.59)	Colorless	65	15
$[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	54.11 (54.04)	4.69 (4.88)	4.66 (4.85)	11.52 (11.32)	Colorless	62	20
$[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	59.99 (60.11)	3.89 (3.85)	4.98 (5.00)	12.32 (12.23)	Colorless	68	17

cm^{-1} , indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The analytical data, color, percentage yield and molar conductance values are given in Table 1.

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra of the compounds display characteristic absorptions due to carboxylate moieties, aniline and pyridine. The solid state infrared spectrum of $[\text{Zn}_2(\text{mal})_2(\text{aniline})_4]$ (**1**) shows prominent bands at 1567, 1372 cm^{-1} corresponding to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of carboxylate groups of malonato ligand. The separation of $\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ between these two bands [$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-) - \nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$] is indicative of monodentate coordination of each carboxylate group¹⁷ of malonato ligand and an overall bidentate bridging coordination. In addition to that **1** also shows bands in the region 700–1300 cm^{-1} arising from vibrational modes of aniline. Infrared spectra of $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**) and $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**) provide evidence for the existence of two different modes of coordination of carboxylate groups. Owing to the presence of the two different coordination modes of carboxylate group in compound **2**, two strong $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ at 1602 and 1557 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ bands at 1455, 1417 cm^{-1} are observed. The bands at 1602 and 1417 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu \sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are assigned to stretching modes of monodentate carboxylate¹⁸. The vibrations observed at 1557 and 1455 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu \sim 102 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are consistent with the presence of bidentate bridging carboxylate groups in the compound^{18,19}. Similarly in the spectrum of $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**) absorptions at 1601 and 1381 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu = 220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are assignable to asymmetric and symmetric modes of monodentate carboxylate, while those observed at 1554 and 1420 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu = 134 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are indicative of bidentate

bridging carboxylate groups. Observance of bands at *ca.* 3130–3179 in **1** and **2** is assignable to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ of aniline. In spectrum of compound **3**, absorption at 1559 cm^{-1} arises due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ of pyridine. Characteristic out of plane deformation band for pyridine was observed at 650 cm^{-1} , shifted to higher frequency compared to free ligand (604 cm^{-1}) suggesting coordination of pyridine nitrogen¹⁹. Appearance of broad band at 3400–3500 cm^{-1} in the compounds is due to $\nu(\text{OH})$. Medium intensity bands in the region 300–500 cm^{-1} are due to M-O and M-N stretching vibrations.

¹H NMR :

¹H NMR spectra of complexes were recorded in CD₃OD. The room temperature ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes do not show any signal due to OH for carboxylic acid (-COOH), which indicate the bonding to metal center through the deprotonated carboxylate oxygens, the IR spectral data also in conformity with the proposition. ¹H NMR spectra of $[\text{Zn}_2(\text{mal})_2(\text{aniline})_4]$ (**1**), $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**) and $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**) show signals in the region δ 6.74, 6.78, 7.43–7.47, 7.85–7.92, 8.54, 8.55 respectively due to aromatic hydrogen atoms of carboxylate as well as nitrogen donors pyridine and aniline, as observed in case of similar zinc complexes¹⁹. In case of compounds **1** and **2** additional signals at δ 2.88, 3.28–3.32 are assignable to -NH₂ proton of aniline. For compound **1** signals in the region 2.08–2.16 is due to -CH₂- proton of malonato ligand. All the observed signals undergo small shift with respect to that from free ligand values and suggest coordination of ligands to the metal center.

ESI mass spectral studies :

ESI mass spectra were recorded for the complexes

$[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**) and $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**). Extensive fragmentation was observed for both complexes. Mass spectral data are in close agreement with the proposed molecular formulae of the synthesized compounds. During fragmentation decarboxylation from the coordination sphere is the major breakdown patterns for the complexes. Elemental analyses and spectral data indicates the presence of water molecules in the complexes, however, the mass spectral pattern did not show direct loss of aqua molecule, indicating that the aqua molecules are rather weakly attached to the metal center as lattice water.

Thus on the basis of chemical analyses in conjunction with spectral studies the following probable molecular structures are proposed for the newly synthesized complexes (Fig. 1).

Antimicrobial property :

The zone of inhibition values of the compounds against the bacteria are summarized in Table 2. Modes of action of metal ions in biological processes are often complex but are believed to involve bonding to heterocyclic residues of biological molecules i.e. proteins, enzymes etc. It has been suggested that compounds with nitrogen and oxygen donor systems inhibit enzyme production as enzymes which require a free hydroxyl group for their activity are especially susceptible to deactivations by ions of complexes²⁰. Coordination reduces the polarity of central metal ion and increases lipophilicity of the complex. This increased lipophilicity enhances the penetration of the complex through lipid layer of the membrane. The observed zone of inhibition data indicate that the complexes are reasonably active against the bacterial species investigated. The result of the study show that $[\text{Zn}_2(\text{mal})_2(\text{aniline})_4]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**) are moderately active against Gram-positive bacteria *B. pumilus* but much less active in case of *S. aureus*, *V.*

$[\text{Zn}_2(\text{mal})_2(\text{aniline})_4]$ (**1**)

$[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**)

$[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**)

Fig. 1. Proposed structures of the complexes.

cholera and *E. coli*, whereas, the compound $[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**) is found to be appreciably active against all the four bacterial strains investigated and exhibit significant antimicrobial activity towards *B. pumilus*.

Table 2. Data for antimicrobial study of compounds

Compound	Inhibition zone diameter (IZD in mm)			
	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>V. cholera</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Tetracycline (Standard)	13.5	14	12	12
$[\text{Zn}_2(\text{mal})_2(\text{aniline})_4]$	12	10	10	9.5
$[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{aniline})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	17	11.5	12	13
$[\text{Zn}_2(4\text{-HOBz})_4(\text{py})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	13.5	9.5	9	9

Conclusion

Syntheses of three new organic-inorganic hybrids containing simple dicarboxylic acid/benzene core carboxylic acid and nitrogen donors viz. aniline, pyridine have been achieved. Although a number of zinc complexes containing nitrogen donors with interesting properties have been reported^{18,19,21}, a rational strategy to synthesize the desired compounds is still a great challenge. The hybrid compounds are usually prepared by hydro/solvo/iono thermal methods²². In the present study synthesis of the hybrids have been achieved by direct and simple method of reaction in aqueous methanol solution at room temperature. The satisfactory analytical data and spectral studies agree well with the composition of the complexes. Although crystal structure data are not available, as single crystal suitable for XRD studies could not be obtained, however, the proposed structures are consistent with the analytical and spectral evidences. Spectral analysis show that in the complexes zinc is tetra coordinated, ligated by monodentate and or bridging bidentate carboxylate oxygen and nitrogen atom of the ancillary ligand aniline or pyridine. The results of antimicrobial studies involving the compounds exhibit moderate to appreciable antimicrobial activity. In addition to the synthetic and structural elucidation, this study also helped to evaluate the potentiality and effectiveness of the complexes to use as antimicrobial agents.

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